

Quantum Two-Slit Interference Applied to a Coin

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In this note we try to develop a toy model of quantum interference applied to a coin. Specifically, we consider a fair coin (with a head and tail side) which rotates from a face up (+1) to a face down (-1) state in space while translating with angular velocity w . The coin also translates with a speed linked to w and the coin diameter. In particular, in one rotation, the coin translates a distance equal to the diameter.

This coin enters a box with a single slot. There are two interaction spots in this box separated by a length equal to the diameter of the box and so the coin interacts with both in a manner which does not change w , but changes the direction of translation. In particular, we suggest a special correlated OR interaction such that if the coin is released and travels at an angle θ_2 with respect to a y axis through the center of the box, then one averages probabilities for each interaction and takes the modulus squared to determine an overall probability for such a θ_2 result.

The following rule is then used. The coin undergoes periodic rotation, but has equal probability to be at any rotation point. Thus, we model the coin by $\exp(i\theta)$, where θ is the angle of the coin with the y axis, by $\exp(i\theta)$, such that the modulus represents 1. $\exp(i\theta)$ is an ordered pair, linked with projections of the coin on the x and y axes. This probability may then be written as $\exp(i c x)$ where x is a distance along the motion ray. The overall effect of the the double interaction in the box is to create an average value $\exp(i c x) + \exp(i c x_1)$ (for each correlated interaction place) for a given angle θ_2 from the y axis going through the center of the box. We suggest that this is an unusual interaction because it is as if probabilistically the entire coin is pulled towards one interaction center or the other and probabilities add, i.e. $\exp(i c x) + \exp(i c x_1)$, where x is linked with distance traveled out along θ_2 from interaction point 1 and x_1 , the distance traveled out along θ_2 from interaction point 2. The interaction itself simply sends the particle out along θ_2 , but there is a probability associated with this sending off, which we discuss in the following paragraph.

This average of the two ordered pairs leads to a single order pair whose modulus squared represents probability. The maximum probability is 4 (i.e. the two rays lined up vertically along the y axis as an example). Once the modulus squared has been calculated for a given angle θ_2 with respect to y , then one may generate a random number from 0 to 4. If it is greater than the modulus squared, a different θ_2 is chosen, otherwise the coin is sent out along θ_2 .

We suggest that this physical model of a coin mimics quantum 2-slit interference and shows the unusual type of interaction which occurs in the 2-slit region. In other words, the double interaction of the coin with both slits (as if the coin were at both places because its diameter (or interaction region) reaches both interaction places) is used to create an average ordered pair whose modulus yields the probability of the coin moving out along θ_2 (which is linked with the two ordered pairs which are averaged). While moving along the ray θ_2 , the coin rotates in its usual manner, just as an $\exp(ipx)$ moves as it usually would.

Two-Slit Interference Using a Coin

The objective of this note is to provide a physical toy model which can produce the same results as quantum two-slit interference. Such a model allows one to examine a physical example of a system which produces two-slit interference and analyse the unusual mechanisms which are required to make such a model work.

We start with a coin with a heads and tail side. The heads side faces forward and is associated with +1 and the tail, with -1. The coin rotates with angular frequency w such that the heads changes to tails in a rotation of 3.14 . We further stipulate that the coin may move such that in one rotation it moves a distance of d , the diameter of the coin.

We allow such a coin to enter a box with a slot. This box has two interaction places separated by d , the diameter of the coin. The coin continues to rotate with w , but each interaction place can change the translation orientation of the coin in the following correlated manner. We consider an angle θ made with a y -axis protruding from the center of the box. This means that if one creates two parallel rays with angle θ from each interaction center, one ray involves extra travel of $d \sin(\theta)$. Because the coin has a diameter, it does not interact at its center, but with both interaction centers.

We now try to model the rotating coin with a probability which shows that each rotation point of the coin has equal probability. This leads to:

$\exp(i \theta)$ ((1)) where θ is the angle the coin face makes with a y -axis.

$\exp(i \theta)$ may be rewritten as: $\exp(i \text{constant} * x)$. ((2))

$\exp(i \theta)$ must be periodic because for every $2 * 3.14$ rotation, the coin is back at the point at which it started.

For a given θ , one may calculate an

$\exp(i \text{constant} * x) + \exp(i \text{constant} * (x + d \sin(\theta)))$ ((3))

(Note: this is an approximation of $\exp(i c x_1) + \exp(i c x_2)$, but is a standard approximation.)

Then: $1 + \cos(d \sin(\theta)) + i \sin(d \sin(\theta)) = 0$ if

$d \sin(\theta) = \text{odd number} * 3.14$ ((4))

This unusual double interaction, however, is only used to calculate a modulus squared of ((3)) associated with a specific θ . The maximum of this number is 4, i.e. 2^2 . Once such a modulus squared is calculated, corresponding to a θ , one chooses a random number between 0 and 4. If this number is greater than the modulus squared, one chooses another θ and repeats the procedure. Otherwise, the rotating coin is sent out along θ . In other words, $\exp(i \theta)$ is a probability which in a double interaction is considered as an OR situation:

$$\exp(i c*x) + \exp(i c*x1) \quad ((5))$$

There is a correlation such that x and $x1$ are both linked with the same θ_2 . An OR situation means that it is as if the coin is pulled to one interaction center and sent along x OR pulled to the other interaction center and sent along $x1$. This is why one sometimes hears that a particle is at two places at once. This interaction, however, is only used to calculate the probability of sending the particle out along θ_2 . There is no tracking of the ray linked with x or $x1$. This type of interaction suggests a probabilistic fluctuation of the entire coin to one interaction place or the other in order to calculate a probability. Once the probability is calculated and a random number chosen between 0 and 4 which is less than or equal to the modulus squared, the coin moves along a θ_2 path without any reference to either interaction center.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to present a toy model of a rotating coin which enters a box with two interaction places separated by the diameter of the coin. The coin translates such that it moves a distance d equal to the diameter during a rotation. The coin is modeled by a probability of $\exp(i \theta) = \exp(i c * x)$. The modulus 1 means that any rotation state of the coin has equal probability, but the periodicity indicates that the coin is rotating and that it may be described by an ordered pair $(\cos(cx), \sin(cx))$ at any instant. This ordered pair is linked to the probability of a state in that its modulus squared equals 1. We suggest that given that the coin has a diameter, it may interact with two interaction places separated by diameter d . This is an OR type of interaction because it is as if the coin is pulled to one interaction center or the other. Each is linked with a different x distance for the same θ_2 , (output angle with respect to a y axis through the center of a box which holds the two interaction places). This unusual OR interaction is only used to calculate a probability associated with a θ_2 using $\exp(i c x) + \exp(i c x2)$, whose modulus squared is then taken. The maximum value is 4 and so a random number is chosen between 0 and 4. If it is less than or equal to the modulus squared, then the coin moves along θ_2 with no information about either interaction center. If not, another θ_2 is chosen and the process repeated. In other words, an unusual interaction occurs in the box. This interaction creates an average of the ordered pair $\exp(i c x)$ with $\exp(i c x1)$ whose modulus squared is taken as the new probability associated with θ_2 . In other words, for a free coin, $\exp(i \theta)$ has the same modulus squared for any θ , but during the interaction, a given θ_2 is linked with an OR average of the two ordered pairs $\exp(i c x)$ and $\exp(i c x1)$ and the ensuing modulus squared yields the a probability for θ_2 . The original θ is the angle the coin face makes with the y -axis (or alternatively with the direction of motion). The new θ_2 is the angle the direction of motion of the coin makes with a fixed y axis. This, however, is due to the ordered pair averaging (i.e. interference).